

SOCIAL AND LEGAL PROTECTION OF MINORAL AFFAIRS EMPLOYEES: ONE OF THE MAIN FACTORS OF ENSURING PUBLIC SAFETY

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to some aspects of social protection of employees of internal affairs bodies. It reveals the legal basis for the organization of social protection of employees.

This is precisely what determines the purpose and meaning of the state's activities, and also sets the task of forming social statehood in the Republic of Uzbekistan. As noted in the regulations, our state is a country that has chosen democracy for itself by the will of its own people. She herself has taken this path and, observing all generally accepted democratic norms, she herself will decide how - taking into account her historical, geopolitical and other specifics - she can ensure the implementation of the principles of freedom and democracy.

According to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the state is a legal, social state, the policy of which is aimed at creating conditions that ensure a decent life and free development of people. There is no doubt that this determines the need to create a reliable and effective system of social and legal protection of the population, including employees of internal affairs bodies and other law enforcement agencies, which reflects one of the basic functions of the state. The problem of social and legal protection of citizens is connected with the functioning of the entire system of factors (positive and negative, general social, regional and group, economic, socio-political, ideological, legal, organizational, etc.), affecting its provision. Existing currently the theory of guarantees of social and legal protection of citizens, as well as rule-making, law enforcement and other practices generally related to human rights predetermine increased attention to them, rethinking and significant adjustments.

This is due primarily to the updating of legislation and the need to bring the functions of the state into line with constitutional and international human rights standards. In conditions of intense confrontation between different social strata against the background of the sharp impoverishment of some and the enrichment of others (which, moreover, is often achieved in far from righteous ways), the state is directly interested in a strong and reliable social system. and legal protection of the individual. Closely related to the formation of a new system of social and legal protection of citizens in the republic in general is the problem of social and legal protection of employees of internal affairs bodies, in particular. The specificity of their activities lies in the fact that, having a wide range of powers in the field of ensuring rights and

the freedoms of citizens from criminal and other attacks, employees of internal affairs bodies often themselves remain unprotected. In addition, service in internal affairs bodies imposes a number of significant restrictions on the legal status of employees. It is especially important to note that in a market economy, an employee of internal affairs bodies cannot engage in entrepreneurial or other paid activities to generate income, with the exception of teaching, scientific and other creative activities.

However, despite the large amount of material concerning the activities of internal affairs bodies in relation to social and the legal protection of their employees, the issue has not received general conceptual coverage. Many scientists have focused their research on very important, but only individual aspects of the problem of social and legal protection of employees of internal affairs bodies, without considering it as a whole.

In this regard, it is advisable to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the problems of social and legal protection of employees of internal affairs bodies, based on a synthesis of domestic and foreign literature and practice and develop the necessary recommendations on this basis. In addition, the following tasks can be set for research in this area:

- determination of the place and role of social and legal protection of citizens in the system of functions of the social state;
- study of laws and other normative legal acts regulating this area of public relations, as well as literature on this issue;
- consideration of the system of factors affecting the state of social and legal protection of citizens;
- study of the legal status of employees of internal affairs bodies in the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- identifying problems of social and legal protection of employees of internal affairs bodies;
- development of a set of measures aimed at ensuring social and legal protection of employees and promoting the rule of law in the activities of internal affairs bodies, etc.

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